

MICRONEEDLES FOR DRUG DELIVERY AND DISEASE DIAGNOSIS

Rui Wang, Rui Yao, Guohua Jiang, Yan Li

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This minimally invasive and painless microneedle technology has the characteristics of simple drug delivery, controllable transdermal delivery, and various drug loading capacities and is a promising drug delivery platform for drug delivery and disease diagnosis. Herein, we comprehensively outline the progress in microneedle technology over the past 10 years from the perspective of classification, design, preparation methods, properties and applications. Two classifications of microneedles, namely, biological and artificial bionic microneedles, are described according to their sources. Consequently, the principles, methods and materials for the shape and structure design of artificial microneedles have been described. The exceptional properties of microneedles have contributed to moving them from curiosity-driven discoveries to practical applications. Special attention has been given to the applications of microneedles in disease diagnosis. These are innovative microneedles that do not contain drugs but imbibe interstitial fluid to monitor continuous health conditions. Therefore, microneedles are expected to become increasingly popular in the field of transdermal drug delivery and flexible wearable devices. Finally, the recent research progresses in drug delivery and disease diagnosis based on microneedle technology developed in our group will be introduced. In the research of microneedle drug delivery, the works are mainly focused on the materials and structural design of microneedles to regulate drug loading rate and delivery rate, thereby regulating blood glucose and uric acid levels in vivo. In the research of disease diagnosis, microneedles can be combined with

other techniques such as iontophoresis, sonophoresis and electrochemical sensing to result in synergistic effects which can be used for blood glucose and ctDNA detection.

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